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The Role of Pescatourism in Enhancing the Competitiveness of the Tourism Sector in the Algerian Coastal Territories: An Analytical Approach

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Abstract

The Algerian coastal territories have very distinctive morphological characteristics, this has helped to develop several activities we find the tourism sector at the forefront. In this context, the study addresses the introduction of Pescatourism as a new ecosystem in Algeria and how can it contribute to increasing coastal territories capacity and competitiveness. The results showed that this activity has significant potential opportunities for the tourism sector, as well as for the fishing sector in Algeria's coastal regions, by increasing competitiveness and economic, social and material absorptive capacity on the one hand, In addition to maintaining artisanal fishing activity as a socio-cultural heritage, on the other hand.

Keywords: Pescatourism, Coastal regions, Fishing, Algeria

1. Introduction

In recent years, coastal places with a strong fishing tradition are trying to promote a new tourism modality (Moreno Muñoz, 2018) and tourism is growing and is developing considerably today. Tourism has become one of the most important economic and social phenomena that occupy an important place in the economies of many developed and developing countries. It is one of the pillars of most of their economies because of its effective contribution to the diversification of national sources of income; Coastal territories are of great importance to the tourism economy, given their very distinct natural resources and potential. Foremost is the landscape of the sea, mountains, sand and living marine resources. Whether the individual is satisfied with his/her job or not is an important determinant for the continuity of the profession (Durgun, Günden, & Ünal, 2021), what has made the relationship between these resources and the activities within them, Coastal tourism is one of the drivers of development on the one hand and the tourism sector is one of the most promising sectors in terms of potential growth, in addition to the foregoing fishing is a key development activity in coastal territories and World

fisheries particularly marine fisheries face many dangers in recent decades (Piasecki, et al., 2016), and to being an extractive primary sector, can play an important role in tourism development and ensure that it has a positive impact on the domestic market primarily. In Algeria artisanal fishery is an ancestral activity, it is a legacy of historical and cultural heritage with over 1600 km of coastline It is already one of the Mediterranean countries where fishing is an essential activity (Guedri & Chakour, 2015).

In this context, we find Pescatourism as an ecosystem activity and an integrated approach linked to several sectors that can contribute to enhancing the competitiveness of the tourism sector within Algeria's coastal territories and increase its absorptive capacity, and Pescatourism is a new eco-tourism approach (Guedri S. E., 2021) its considered one of the most innovative activities of the coastal fishing system (Saba, 2013) , and he should be considered different activity from fisheries tourism or recreational fishing (Piasecki, et al., 2016) , especially as the marine ecosystems are undergoing major transformations due to the establishment and spread of Non-Indigenous Species (Kleitou, et al., 2021) and it is a relatively new development in sustainable tourism, becoming established in the early 1990s in Italy (Lai, Gianna, & Del Giudice, 2016), in 1992 Italy became the first nation within the EU and the Mediterranean Sea area to allow tourism trips onboard professional fishing boats (Romanelli & Meliado, 2021).

The importance of this study is to highlight the role played by Pescatourism in diversifying the tourism sector's resources by attracting tourists and increasing their capacity within coastal territories and thus increasing competitiveness within the tourism sector.

This article attempts, therefore, to answer the question: *How can Pescatourism contribute to improving the attractiveness of Algeria's coastal territories and increasing the competitiveness of its tourism sector?*

To answer to this question we have formulated the following hypothesis: *Pescatourism can contribute to increasing the attractiveness of Algeria's coastal territories and increasing the competitiveness of its tourism sector by increasing its absorptive capacity - economic, material and social- as well as being a tourist show that enters the experience economy where experience is integrated into the valuation process of goods and services to provide tourist services and new experiences for tourists.*

The descriptive analytical method was used in this research, using theoretical concepts of Pescatourism as an integrated approach, as well as the presentation of mathematical equations demonstrating how this approach has contributed to enhancing the competitiveness of the tourism sector in the Algerian coastal regions.

2. Pescatourism Concepts:

Pescatourism emerged as a new development in sustainable tourism in the early 1990 in Italy, with many definitions, the most important of which can be mentioned as follows:

- **Pecatourism** is a supplementary diversionary activity for marine fishing activity, where tourists are transported on fishing boats to discover the occupation of artisanal fishermen as well as the discovery of the sea world, so that the fishing activity remains the main (Guedri S. E., 2017).

- **Pecatourism** is a new eco-tourism approach that gives fishermen the opportunity to welcome tourists aboard their boats, to make them discover their fishing activity and the practices of an ancestral profession (Guedri S. E., 2021).

- **Pecatourism** is trips on fishing boat with local fishermen take tourists on board, where tourists participate in the fishing process by throwing and pulling nets and performing other tasks, such as eating fresh fish cooked on board and visiting fishing villages (Lai, Gianna, & Del Giudice, 2016).

- **Pecatourism** is "the transport of passengers carried out on board a professional fishing or aquaculture vessel with the aim of making the latter discover the profession of shellfish farmer or fisherman and the marine environment in a manner concomitant with the activity and not linked to remuneration for this benefit." (Baranger, Benceny, Bigot, & Le Bihan, 2012).

Based on the foregoing, Pescatourism can be defined as: a kind of responsible travel to marine spaces that contributes to the preservation of the marine environment and ensures improved welfare of artisanal fishermen in order for artisanal fishermen to receive a number of tourists on board their boat and make them discover their profession and various traditional practices, Pescatourism can therefore be regarded as a new and authentic ecosystem with fishermen aboard their boats using humanitarian activity within a distinctive natural environment and thus increasing the tourism sector's competitiveness within coastal territories.

It is characterized as a joint activity between three main sectors: artisanal fishing, tourism and the environment; If offshore fishing is an initial activity based on the extraction of fish resources using appropriate equipment vessels and fishing equipment, the tourism sector is a more complex activity, as it is based on a series of services provided by tourist companies as well as elements and natural conditions such as: accommodation, transport, climate, historical sites, landscapes, etc., and therefore Pescatourism can be considered as a tourist activity applied from the traditional human activity of "artisanal hunting" rich in a great cultural and social heritage, and within the framework of a distinctive natural environment.

1.1 Pescatourism in Algeria

Pescatourism or tourist marine fishing is a recent occurrence, where it was established after the issuance of the Executive Decree of 16-203 of 25 July 2016, which sets out the conditions and qualifications for the exercise of urban shipping and maritime activities this Decree defines this activity in article three as: « Passenger fishing on ships equipped for sea fishing or water vessels as a complementary picnic activity in order to discover the profession of fishermen or aquaculture breeders and so on»(Official Journal No. 44 of 2016).

The organization of Pescatourism in Algeria can be explained in the following format:

Figure 1: Organization of Pescatourism in Algeria

Source: realized by the authors, based on Executive Decree of 16-203.

3. Pescatourism contribution to the development of the tourism sector in Algeria's coastal territories

The tourism sector is one of the few sectors that continues to grow in the world despite various crises, as the interests of tourists in the territories have transcended their traditional concept based on the sun and the beach, where Pescatourism as an activity can develop the tourism sector and the fishing sector as taking into account the

specificities of local fishing from heritage and traditions, as well as educating and familiarizing tourists with methods.

Figure 2: Pescatourism contribution to the sustainable development of the tourism sector in coastal territories

Source: realized by the authors, based on (Guedri S. E., 2017)

Pescatourism has great importance for the tourism sector, as it is an ecosystem that offers new tourism offers as well as old ones, thus contributing to the development of the tourism sector especially in the Algerian coastal territories, towards sustainable local tourism development.

4. Pescatourism contribution to enhancing the Territories competitiveness and increasing its absorptive capacity.

Ostensibly, the term competitiveness seems to be a simple concept. According to the Oxford dictionary, the word competitiveness is derived from the Latin word "competitit", which was in the early 19th century. According to the World Economic Forum Global Competitiveness Report, competitiveness was defined as: "The range of institutions, policies and factors determining the level of productivity in a country", and from the perspective of "Franziska Blurk" competitiveness can be defined as "the ability to provide more efficient and effective products and services than competitors in the field" (Guedri S. E., 2017), competitiveness has a direct bearing on the attractiveness of the Territory, which is a multifaceted concept, defined as the Territory's ability to attract various factors of production and/or population, and thus the Territory's ability to be chosen by a particular actor as a temporary or permanent location by "moral persons or individuals" (Guedri S. E., 2017) and one of the problems presented by the marine is fishing tourism (Moreno Muñoz, 2018).

According to the World Tourism Organization, "OMT", absorptive capacity is "levels that can be maintained without destroying the physical environment and without generating social, cultural and economic problems for society"... This definition includes a set of sub-definitions, where each definition represents a particular area as follows:

- ✓ **Physical absorptive capacity:** This sub-concept shows the damage tourism can cause to the environment as a result of the inappropriate behavior of tourists "pollution, excessive water consumption, loss of greenery... etc."
- ✓ **Social absorptive capacity:** We deal with this concept with the two pivotal parties in the field of tourism "Tourists and the host community", since the capacity of the host community expresses the maximum tolerance, actions and demands of the alien without the sense of pressure, coercion or psychological harm, while the capacity for tourists is affected by their customs, principles and distortion, as the origin in tourism is to enrich the tourist's knowledge and not to abandon/or abolish his original heritage and beliefs.
- ✓ **Economic absorptive capacity:** This concept means that tourism does not adversely affect various economic activities, in terms of non-price manipulation, raw materials, non-monopoly of transport by tourism companies... etc.

In this context, Pescatourism can provide the addition in the field of physical absorptive capacity, economic and social, as follows:

Figure 3: The role of Pescatourism in increasing the absorptive capacity and attractiveness of coastal territories.

Source: realized by the authors, based on (Guedri S. E., 2017)

5. Method and Tools

Thus, the Territory's absorptive capacity is strictly commensurate with ecosystems, which serve to refine the behavior of tourists and develop the culture of environmental consumption and the behavior of tourists that takes into account the requirements of ecosystems, as well as economic and social absorptive capacity. In this context we find artisanal fishing as a highly inherited activity, based on fishing techniques distinct from other modern fishing gear, an important attraction that can contribute to enhancing the Territory's competitiveness and increasing its attractiveness.

The relationship between Pescatourism and the Territory's attractiveness and the development of local tourism can be explained mathematically as follows:

We have:

N_t : Number of tourists;

A_t :The Territory's attractiveness;

D_{pt} : Developing the activity of Pescatourism; It is a function of the number of artisanal fishermen who engage in this ecosystem approach;

N_{t0} : Number of tourists in the absence of Pescatourism activity;

A_{t0} : The Territory's attractiveness in the absence of Pescatourism activity;

N_{pa} : Number of artisanal fishermen engaged in this activity.

Figure 4: Relationship between Pescatourism, the Territory's attractiveness and local tourism development.

Source:(Guedri S. E., 2017)

6. Results and Discussion

We note through the curve that there is an expulsive correlation between the attractiveness of the Territory and the number of tourists, as increasing the attractiveness of the Territory in the application of the tourism activity will create added value as follows:

$$\Delta N_t = N_{t2} - N_{t1} \quad (01)$$

In addition, the Territory's "especially physical" absorptive capacity in the presence of Pescatourism will increase, as this ecosystem approach will contribute to the development of ecosystem culture and the preservation of the state of the coastal environment with all its multiple environmental wealth. This increases the Territory's "especially environmental" absorptive capacity as follows:

$$\Delta A_t = A_{t2} - A_{t1} \quad (02)$$

$$A_t = f(D_{pt}) = \beta \cdot D_{pt} + A_{t0} \quad (03)$$

$$N_t = f(D_{pt}) = \alpha \cdot D_{pt} + N_{t0} \quad (04)$$

$$\alpha = tg\alpha = \Delta N_t / \Delta D_{pt} = (N_{t2} - N_{t1}) / (D_{pt2} - D_{pt1}) \quad (05)$$

$$\beta = tg\beta = \Delta A_t / \Delta D_{pt} = (A_{t2} - A_{t1}) / (D_{pt2} - D_{pt1}) \quad (06)$$

Through the above figure, artisanal fishermen's incomes are directly commensurate with the number of **Pescatourists** as follows:

We have:

N_{pt} : Number of Pescatourists;

Y_p : Artisanal fishermen's income.

Where: $Y_p = f(N_{pt}) \quad (07)$

Figure 5: The relationship between the number of Pescatourists and the income of artisanal fishermen.

Source: realized by the authors, the results of our research.

The above figure shows us the parcel relationship between the tourist flow and the incomes of artisanal fishermen, as an increase in the number of tourists as part of the valuation of artisanal fishing activity "Pscatourists" will increase the incomes of fishermen. The relationship between the two variables can be written as follows:

$$Y_p = f(N_{pt}) = a \cdot N_{pt} + b \quad (08)$$

Where:

b = Artisanal fishermen's income in case the number of Pescatourists is equal to zero;

a = tendency.

Where:

$$a = tga = \Delta Y / \Delta N_{pt} = (Y_{p2} - Y_{p1}) / (N_{pt2} - N_{pt1}) \quad (09)$$

Our equation number (04):

$$N_{pt} = f(D_{pt}) = \alpha \cdot D_{pt} \quad (10)$$

Where:

$$\alpha = \Delta N_t / \Delta D_{pt} = (N_{t2} - N_{t1}) / (D_{pt2} - D_{pt1})$$

From (10) and (08) we find that:

$$Y_p = f(N_{pt}) = a \cdot N_{pt} + b = a \cdot [\alpha \cdot D_{pt}] + b \quad (11)$$

As a result of the Territory's increased attractiveness, as a result of the valuation of artisanal fishing activity in tourism, the incomes of artisanal fishermen will increase as follows:

$$\Delta Y = Y_2 - Y_1 \quad (11)$$

Where:

$$Y_1 = f(N_{t1}) = a \cdot N_{t1} + b = a \cdot [\alpha \cdot D_{pt1}] + b \quad (12)$$

$$Y_2 = f(N_{t2}) = a \cdot N_{t2} + b = a \cdot [\alpha \cdot D_{pt2}] + b \quad (13)$$

From (11), (12) and (13) we find that:

$$\Delta Y = a \cdot N_{t1} + b - a \cdot N_{t2} - b = a(N_{t1} - N_{t2}) \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta Y = a \cdot [\alpha \cdot D_{pt2}] - a \cdot [\alpha \cdot D_{pt1}] = a \cdot \alpha [D_{pt2} - D_{pt1}] \quad (15)$$

We also have: Developing the activity of Pscatourism as a function of the number of artisanal fishermen who engage in this ecosystem activity.

Where:

$$D_{pt} = M(N_{pa}) = \phi \cdot N_{pa} \quad (16)$$

From (15) and (16) we find that:

$$\Delta Y = a \cdot \alpha [D_{pt2} - D_{pt1}] = a \cdot \alpha \cdot \phi [N_{pa2} - N_{pa1}] \quad (17)$$

Where:

$$a = tga = \Delta Y / \Delta N_t = (Y_2 - Y_1) / (N_{t2} - N_{t1}) \quad (18)$$

$$\alpha = tg\alpha = \Delta N_t / \Delta D_{pt} = (N_{t2} - N_{t1}) / (D_{pt2} - D_{pt1}) \quad (19)$$

$$\phi = tg\phi = \Delta D_{pt} / \Delta N_{pa} = (D_{pt2} - D_{pt1}) / (N_{pa2} - N_{pa1}) \quad (20)$$

Through the above, it can be said that exploiting and valuing artisanal fishing as a sociocultural activity in the tourism sector will contribute to local tourism development, and the development of Pescatourism will also enhance the territory's competitiveness and absorptive capacity, resulting in returns for the territory as a whole, the so-called multiplier effect, as well as enhance the survival of this activity by protecting its authenticity and enhancing the confidence of artisan fishermen in its membership.

7. Conclusion

As discussed in this study, we have seen how important Pescatourism is as a new ecosystem that contributes to supporting and enhancing the competitiveness of coastal territories by increasing their absorptive capacity on the one hand, as well as preserving marine ecosystems by keeping pressure on fishery resources and developing a behavior that takes into account ecosystems requirements; It thus contributes to the achievement of sustainable local tourism development on the one hand, and the preservation of fishing activity and all its cultural components on the other. This activity also contributes significantly to the achievement of food security, increased national wealth, national income, economic output levels and the creation of positions of employment, since relieving pressure on fisheries resources achieved through this activity will allow fisheries resources to proliferate rapidly.

8. Results

In Algeria, the public authorities are working today to give effect to the legal provisions concerning the dissemination of this activity to the coastal states in the framework of various projects with artisan fishermen and in the framework of marine reserves, as part of a participatory consultative process between the various actors involved in this project, as well as a multidisciplinary approach to ensure that all those involved in this project benefit.

9. Recommendations

As recommendations we propose to enhance the competitiveness of the tourism sector in the coastal regions through the Pescatourism activity in Algeria:

- Take advantage of various global experiences in this activity, especially Italy's experience in these projects;
- The need to strengthen existing artisanal fishing units for this activity and to avoid the establishment of new fishing units, this will spur this approach from its true content;
- Encouraging tourist agencies to promote and approach this activity and to grant them fiscal and financial concessions in case of attracting a large number of tourists in the context of this activity;
- The need for all actors to participate in this activity by contributing to its explanation, definition and promotion, also to ensure the success of this project;
- Focus on the composition of artisanal fishermen in this activity;
- Coordinating various sectors active in this area, such as fishing, tourism, the environment, transport and forestry, in order to sustain this activity and to support policies to develop the tourism sector and enhance its competitiveness in coastal territories and thereby generate financial returns in hard currency for the public treasury outside the revenues of the petroleum sector.

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